

Synthesis, molecular and crystalline architectures of mononuclear nickel(II) and cadmium(II) complexes containing a hexadentate Schiff base

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Abstract : Mononuclear compounds of the types $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**1**) and $[\text{Cd}(\text{L})](\text{PF}_6)_2$ (**2**) [$\text{L} = N^1$ -(2-(3-(phenyl(pyridin-2-yl)methyleneamino)propylamino)ethyl)- N^3 -(phenyl(pyridin-2-yl)methylene)propane-1,3-diamine)] have been isolated using one-pot reactions of appropriate molar ratio of the building components in MeOH solutions at room temperature and are characterized by microanalytical, spectroscopic and other physico-chemical results. X-Ray crystallographic studies of **1** and **2** were made to define the coordination sphere. The metal(II) center in **1/2** adopts a distorted octahedral coordination environment with two pyridine N atoms and two amine N atoms of L in the equatorial plane and remaining two imine N atoms occupying the axial positions. In crystalline states, individual units in **1/2** are associated through weak cooperative N-H...O/F hydrogen bonds resulting in 1D helical/1D zig-zag chain. In MeCN solution, **1** shows a quasi-reversible one-electron oxidative response corresponding to nickel(II)-nickel(III) couple. Both the compounds display $^1(\pi-\pi^*)$ fluorescence in DMF solutions at room temperature.

Keywords : Nickel(II), cadmium(II), Schiff base, X-ray structure, luminescence.

Introduction

Recently, considerable attention has been focused on the coordination chemistry¹⁻³ of Schiff bases because of their ease of preparation, structural varieties and varied denticities. The complexes show a range of applications such as catalysts^{2,4}, magnetic materials⁵, porous materials⁶, luminous materials⁷, electronic and optoelectronic devices⁸ and modeling biological processes⁹. We are also active¹⁰⁻¹² in isolation of various transition and non-transition metal Schiff base compounds of varied molecular and crystalline architectures coupled with interesting magnetic and luminescence properties. In the present endeavour, the chemistry of a hexadentate N-donor Schiff base, N^1 -(2-(3-(phenyl(pyridin-2-yl)methyleneamino)propylamino)ethyl)- N^3 -(phenyl(pyridin-2-yl)methylene)propane-1,3-diamine (L, Scheme 1) with symmetrical $N^p, N^i, N^a, N^a, N^i, N^p$ backbone towards nickel(II) and cadmium(II) ions have been investigated in building of new molecular architectures and superstructures. We have successfully isolated two mono-

nuclear compounds $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**1**) and $[\text{Cd}(\text{L})](\text{PF}_6)_2$ (**2**). The details of syntheses, structures, and luminescence behaviours are described below.

Scheme 1. Structure of L.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

Hexacoordinated mononuclear compounds **1** and **2** were obtained in good yields using one-pot synthesis of 1 : 1 : 1 metal(II) acetates, hexadentate Schiff base (L) and appropriate counter anions in MeOH solutions at room temperature. The air-stable moisture-insensitive com-

pounds are crystalline and soluble in a range of common organic solvents such as MeOH, EtOH, MeCN, DMF and DMSO but are insoluble in H₂O. In DMF solutions, **1** and **2** show conductivity values (see Experimental) corresponding to 2 : 1 electrolytic behavior¹³. Room temperature solid-phase magnetic susceptibility measurement shows that **1** has magnetic moment value 2.83 BM close to the spin-only ($S = 1$) value (2.82 BM) expected for a discrete and magnetically non-coupled mononuclear $3d^8$ ion.

Spectroscopic studies :

In IR spectra, complexes **1** and **2** show strong absorption bands in the range 1625–1595 cm⁻¹ assignable to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N}) + \nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ stretching vibrations of the metal bound Schiff base. The presence of perchlorate and hexafluorophosphate stretches respectively in **1** and **2** (see Experimental) is indicative of their non-coordination¹⁴ to the metal centers. DMF solution of **1** exhibits two $d-d$ bands at 893 and 545 nm representing spin-allowed ${}^3T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ and ${}^3T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ transitions, respectively and the shoulder at 809 nm originating from spin-forbidden ${}^1E_g \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ transition, frequently observed in nickel(II) octahedral complexes¹⁵. Additionally, ligand based transitions at 279 nm in **1** and at 282 nm in **2** are observed.

Luminescence properties :

The photoluminescence behaviours of the free ligand (L) and its compounds (**1** and **2**) are examined in DMF solutions. The nature of the emission spectra of L, **1** and **2** are depicted in Fig. 1. Upon photo-excitation at 270 nm, L exhibits a fluorescent emission centered at 305 nm. The compounds **1** and **2**, upon photo-excitation at ~280 nm show less intense photoluminescence with the main emissions at 302 and 300 nm, respectively. The luminescence behaviour in **1** and **2** may be attributed to an intraligand ${}^1(\pi-\pi^*)$ emission^{16,17}. The systematic decrease in the intensity values on going from **1** to **2** may lie in the heavy metal effect¹⁸.

Electrochemical study :

The electroactivity of **1** was examined in MeCN solution using CV at a platinum working electrode. **1** shows quasi-reversible ($\Delta E_p = 252$ mV) oxidative response presumably due to Ni^{II}-Ni^{III} couple as shown in eq. (1) :

The response is reproducible with no trace of decomposition after a number of cycles. The formal potential is ca. 0.67 V versus Ag/AgCl electrode. One-electron nature of the couple was verified with comparison of standard sample¹⁹.

Fig. 1. Emission spectra of L, **1** and **2** in DMF solutions at room temperature.

Crystal structure of **1** and **2** :

In order to define the coordination sphere conclusively, single-crystal X-ray diffraction study of **1** and **2** were made. ORTEP diagrams with atom numbering scheme of the cation in **1** and **2** are shown in Fig. 2. Selected interatomic bond lengths and bond angles are listed in Table 1. Significant hydrogen bond parameters are set in Table 2.

Structural analyses reveal that **1/2** crystallizes in a trigonal/orthorhombic system with R-3/Pbcn space group. The coordination polyhedron around the metal center in **1/2** is best described as a distorted octahedron with an MN₆ chromophore (M = Ni in **1** and M = Cd in **2**). Two N^p atoms (N1, N2 in **1** and N1, N6 in **2**) and N^a atoms (N5, N6 in **1** and N3, N4 in **2**) of L define the equatorial plane, whereas remaining two Nⁱ atoms (N3, N4 in **1** and N2, N5 in **2**) occupy the axial sites. The hexadentate Schiff base (L) form three five-membered and two six-membered chelate loops with smaller bite angles [69.97(16)–76.59(19)° and 84.64(21)–86.57(17)°] in **2** compared to that [77.25(11)–83.71(13)° and 91.07(13)–91.88(13)°] in **1** (Table 1). L is twisted around the M(II) center such that the two planes containing the unsaturated

Fig. 2. ORTEP representations of **1** (top) and **2** (bottom) with atom numbering schemes and 30% thermal ellipsoid probability for non-hydrogen atoms.

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (°) for **1** and **2**

Bond distances for 1		Bond distances for 2	
Ni1-N1	2.103(3)	Cd1-N1	2.337(5)
Ni1-N2	2.102(3)	Cd1-N2	2.414(5)
Ni1-N3	2.122(3)	Cd1-N3	2.351(6)
Ni1-N4	2.125(3)	Cd1-N4	2.351(5)
Ni1-N5	2.100(3)	Cd1-N5	2.424(5)
Ni1-N6	2.107(3)	Cd1-N6	2.297(4)
Bond angles for 1		Bond angles for 2	
N5-Ni1-N2	167.05(13)	N6-Cd1-N4	152.97(17)
N1-Ni1-N6	167.57(12)	N1-Cd1-N3	150.52(19)
N3-Ni1-N4	172.00(12)	N2-Cd1-N5	163.01(18)
N1-Ni1-N3	77.25(11)	N1-Cd1-N2	70.04(16)
N2-Ni1-N4	77.60(12)	N3-Cd1-N2	84.64(21)
N5-Ni1-N6	83.71(13)	N4-Cd1-N3	76.59(19)
N6-Ni1-N3	91.88(13)	N4-Cd1-N5	86.57(17)
N2-Ni1-N1	96.46(11)	N6-Cd1-N5	69.97(16)
N2-Ni1-N6	90.68(12)	N6-Cd1-N3	98.87(19)
N5-Ni1-N4	91.07(13)	N1-Cd1-N4	94.77(19)
N5-Ni1-N1	91.24(12)	N6-Cd1-N1	100.83(18)

Table 2. Hydrogen bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for **1** and **2**

Compd.	D-H...A	D-H	H...A	D...A	D-H...A
1	N5-H5D...O8 ^a	0.88	2.22	3.082(6)	164
	N6-H6D...O7 ^b	0.79	2.53	3.224(7)	148
2	N3-H3A...F8 ^c	0.91	2.31	3.185(9)	161
	N4-H4A...F10 ^d	1.00	2.09	3.069(9)	165

Symmetry codes : a = 1-x, 1-y, 1-z; b = 1/3+y, 5/3-x+y, 2/3-z; c = x, y, -1+z; d = 1/2-x, 3/2-y, -1/2+z.

chelate rings (Ni1, N1, C5, C6, N3 in **1** and Cd1, N1, C5, C6, N3 in **2**) and (Ni1, N2, C28, C21, N4 in **1** and Cd1, N5, C21, C28, N6 in **2**) are inclined to each other at 78.93° in **1** and 75.55° in **2**. The propylenic arm of L in the saturated six-membered chelate ring is to some extent puckered. M(II)-N distances²⁰ lie in the range 2.100(3)-2.125(3) Å in **1** and 2.297(4)-2.424(5) Å in **2**; in both cases the equatorial bond distances [2.100(3)-2.107(3) Å in **1** and 2.297(4)-2.351(5) Å in **2**] are somewhat shorter than the [2.122(3)-2.125(3) Å in **1** and 2.414(5)-2.424(5) Å in **2**] axial bond lengths. Metal centers are displaced out of the mean equatorial plane by 0.002 Å in **1** and by 0.006 Å for **2**. Among the four equatorial atoms, N1 and N6 in **1**/N1 and N3 in **2** deviate (N1 : 0.188 Å and N3 : 0.212 Å in **1** and N1 : 0.445 Å and N3 : 0.558 Å in **2**) towards N3 in **1**/N2 in **2** whereas N2 and N5 in **1**/N4 and N6 in **2** show considerable deviation (N2 : 0.189 Å and N5 : 0.211 Å in **1** and N4 : 0.572 Å and N6 : 0.431 Å in **2**) towards N4 in **1**/N5 in **2** from the mean plane.

In crystalline states, individual units in **1** are assembled through weak cooperative N-H...O hydrogen bonds affording a 1D helical chain along *c*-axis (Fig. 3a). In contrast, a 1D zig-zag chain (Fig. 3b) in **2** is formed through weak cooperative N-H...F hydrogen bonds (Table 2). H atoms (H5D and H6D in **1** and H3A and H4A in **2**) of -NH- groups of L and O atoms (O7 and O8) of ClO₄⁻ ions/F atoms (F8 and F10) of PF₆⁻ ions are involved in such hydrogen bondings. The inter-chain Ni...Ni separation (8.796 Å) in **1** is shorter than inter-chain Cd...Cd distance (10.773 Å) in **2**.

Conclusion :

Two new mononuclear nickel(II) and cadmium(II) complexes in combination with a hexadentate Schiff base (L) are isolated and X-ray crystallographically characterized. A change in crystalline architectures with variation of

Fig. 3. Views of (a) 1D helical chain in **1** and (b) 1D zig-zag chain in **2** formed through N-H...O (in **1**) and N-H...F (in **2**) hydrogen bonds running along crystallographic *c*-axis.

central metal ions as well as counter ions is observed in going from **1** to **2**.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity 2-benzoylpyridine (Lancaster, UK), *N,N'*-bis(3-aminopropyl)ethane-1,3-diamine (Spectrochem, India), nickel(II) acetate (SRL, India), cadmium(II) acetate (SRL, India), sodium perchlorate (Lancaster, UK) and ammonium hexafluorophosphate (Fluka, Germany) were purchased from respective concerns and used as received. The Schiff base, *N*¹-(2-(3-(phenyl(pyridin-2-yl)methyleneamino)propylamino)ethyl)-*N*³-(phenyl(pyridin-2-yl)methylene)propane-1,3-diamine (**L**) belonging to symmetrical N^P, Nⁱ, N^a, N^a Nⁱ, N^P type backbone, [N^P = N(pyridine), Nⁱ = N(imine) and N^a = N(amine)] was prepared by condensation of 1 : 2 molar ratio of *N,N'*-bis(3-aminopropyl)ethane-1,3-diamine and 2-benzoylpyridine following a reported method²⁰. All other chemicals and solvents used were AR grade. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air.

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were done using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) were

recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer. Molar conductances were measured using a Systronics conductivity meter where the cell constant was calibrated with 0.01 M KCl solution and dry DMF was used as solvent. Room temperature magnetic susceptibilities were measured on a CAHN electrobalance 7550 with Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as a reference and diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants²¹. Electrochemical measurements were made with a computer controlled CH (Model CHI620D) electrochemical instrument using dry MeCN as solvent and tetrabutylammonium perchlorate as supporting electrolyte. Platinum and Ag/AgCl were respectively the working and the reference electrodes in the process. The following parameters and relations were used : scan rate (*v*), 100 mV s⁻¹; formal potential $E^{\circ} = 0.5(E_{pa} + E_{pc})$ where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are anodic and cathodic peak potentials, respectively; ΔE_p is the peak-to-peak separation. The potentials were referenced to an Ag/AgCl electrode. Ground state absorption and steady-state fluorescence measurements (in DMF) were made with a Shimadzu model UV-2450 UV-Vis spectrophotometer and a Hitachi model F-4010 spectrofluorimeter, respectively.

Synthesis of [Ni(L)](ClO₄)₂ (**1**) and [Cd(L)](PF₆)₂ (**2**) :

A methanolic solution (15 ml) of faint yellow **L** (0.252 g, 0.5 mmol) was added dropwise to a green methanolic solution (15 ml) of Ni(CH₃COO)₂·4H₂O (0.124 g, 0.5 mmol). To this resulting yellowish-green solution, a methanolic solution (30 ml) of NaClO₄ (0.070 g, 0.5 mmol) was added slowly. The final solution was filtered and left for slow evaporation in air at room temperature. After a week fine brown microcrystalline product of **1** that separated, was washed with toluene and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield : 0.55 g (72%). Similarly, pure **2** has been isolated [yield : 0.63 g (70%)] following the above procedure except Cd(CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O (0.133 g, 0.5 mmol) instead of Ni(CH₃COO)₂·4H₂O and NH₄PF₆ (0.092 g, 0.5 mmol) instead of NaClO₄ were used.

Anal. Calcd. for C₃₂H₃₆N₆O₈Cl₂Ni (**1**) : C, 50.4; H, 4.8; N, 11.0. Found : C, 50.2; H, 4.8; N, 10.9%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N}) + \nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ 1618, 1595; $\nu(\text{ClO}_4)$ 1118, 1106, 1088, 624; Λ_M (DMF, $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) : 220; UV-Vis in DMF (λ , nm) : 893, 809, 545, 279; μ_{eff} : 2.83 BM. Anal. Calcd. for C₃₂H₃₆N₆F₁₂P₂Cd (**2**) : C,

42.4; H, 4.0; N, 9.3. Found : C, 42.3; H, 3.9; N, 9.3%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N}) + \nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ 1622, 1597; $\nu(\text{PF}_6)$ 844, 558; Λ_{M} (DMF, $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) : 225; UV-Vis in DMF (λ , nm) : 282.

X-Ray crystallography :

Diffraction data of the single crystals of **1** and **2** were collected at 150(2) K and 296(2) K, respectively on a Bruker SMART CCD area-detector diffractometer using graphite monochromated Mo-K α radiation (0.71073 Å). The empirical absorption corrections were based on multi-scan data. The structures were solved by direct methods using SHELXS-97²² and refined by SHELXL-97²². All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters whereas hydrogen atoms were lo-

cated geometrically and refined using a standard riding model. For compound **1**, the one -CH₂ and one -CH- groups are disordered over two orientations (occupancies are 0.60 and 0.40 for C14, H14A, H14B and C14A, H14D, H14E respectively; 0.50 and 0.50 for C24, H24 and C24A, H24D, respectively). Two O atoms of a ClO₄⁻ unit are also disordered over two positions with the fractional occupancies of 0.80 and 0.20 for O5, O8 and O5A, O8A, respectively. Further crystallographic details are given in Table 3.

Supplementary materials :

Crystallographic data (excluding structure factors) for **1** and **2** have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre Nos. 883753 and 883754, respec-

Table 3. Crystallographic data for [Ni(L)](ClO₄)₂ (**1**) and [Cd(L)](PF₆)₂ (**2**)

Crystallographic parameter	1	2
Empirical formula	C ₃₂ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₈ Cl ₂ Ni	C ₃₂ H ₃₆ N ₆ F ₁₂ P ₂ Cd
Formula weight	764.31	907.02
Temperature (K)	150(2)	296(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073	0.71073
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.235 × 0.221 × 0.210	0.321 × 0.301 × 0.275
Crystal system	Trigonal	Orthorhombic
Space group	R-3	Pbcn
<i>D</i> (cal) (g/cm ³)	1.376	1.596
Volume (Å ³)	16558(3)	7464.4(8)
<i>Z</i>	18	8
Unit cell dimension :		
<i>a</i> (Å)	34.7984(16)	28.2559(19)
<i>b</i> (Å)	34.7984(16)	14.4544(9)
<i>c</i> (Å)	15.7891(15)	18.2762(12)
α (°), β (°), γ (°)	90, 90, 120	90, 90, 90
<i>T</i> _{max} and <i>T</i> _{min}	0.858 and 0.843	0.811 and 0.783
<i>F</i> (000)	7128	6106
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.728	0.763
θ range for data collection (°)	1.46, 28.00	1.44 to 26.41
<i>h</i> / <i>k</i> / <i>l</i>	-38,45/-45,36/-20,18	-35,35/-18,18/-15,22
Reflections collected	42705	48460
Independent reflections	8908 [R(int) = 0.0809]	7650 [R(int) = 0.0749]
Data/restraints/parameters	8908/2/460	7650/2/470
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	0.948	1.020
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	R1 = 0.0591, wR2 = 0.1482	R1 = 0.0624, wR2 = 0.1893
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	R1 = 0.1455, wR2 = 0.1754	R1 = 0.1031, wR2 = 0.2152
Largest peak and hole (eÅ ⁻³)	0.515 and -0.491	2.489 and -0.565
R1 = $\Sigma F_o - F_c / \Sigma F_o $, wR2 = $[\Sigma w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2/\Sigma w(F_o^2)]^{1/2}$, calcd. w = $1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0857P)^2 + 0.0000P]$ for 1 ; calcd. w = $1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.1285P)^2 + 0.0000P]$ for 2 ; where P = $(F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$.		

tively. Copies of this information can be obtained, free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : 44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

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